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Leveraging art markets by artists from Africa with a special interest in the Kenyan art scene: The discrete charm of the NFTs from an artist's perspective^{*}

Abstract: This paper offers an overview of the African art scene, with a special focus on the Kenyan art scene. It will also examine non-fungible tokens (NFTs) as a new marketing tool and platform for artists from Africa, exploring how this technology has diversified artistic practices through experimentation beyond traditional painting and sculpture to video, performance art, installations, photography, and digital media. The paper does not delve into the technicalities of creating NFTs but presents an overview and experiences based on conversations with artists and a gallery owner based in Kenya. It also highlights key marketplaces available for minting and marketing NFTs online, noting those most popularly used by artists from Africa.

Keywords: African art, NFT marketplaces, artists collectives, art galleries, art studios, art education, art distribution

Overview of how the NFTs work

Generative NFT collections have taken off in recent months, with all kinds of copycats and twists launching to take advantage of the hype. After its debut, Bored Apes Yacht Club quickly became the second-biggest name in NFT collections, right behind CryptoPunks.

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Hossein Naderi introduces a decentralized application that utilizes blockchain and computer vision to incentivize construction safety through token rewards.¹ The application autonomously evaluates safety performance and issues unique non-fungible tokens (NFTs) as rewards while maintaining user confidentiality. While it presents promising prospects for various domains, scalability issues and challenges related to individual incentivization must be addressed through further development to expand its practical applications.

An NFT is “a unique digital item stored on a blockchain” and “can represent almost anything,” for example art, collectibles, profile pictures, and event tickets for events, and “serve as a digital record of ownership.” The difference between fungibility and non-fungibility is that fungible items are “interchangeable with another of the same item,” such as a \$1, whereas a non-fungible item “has its own unique value” because the item is “totally unique.” On OpenSea, minting “is the process of writing a digital item to the blockchain” through which “its immutable record of authenticity and ownership” is established.²

Ethereum was conceived around 2014 and launched in 2015 to extend the concept of Bitcoin. Ethereum has its own currency, Ether (ETH), just like Bitcoin (BTC), but the platform can run any set of instructions, not just “send and receive Bitcoin.”³ Since Ethereum declared itself “a decentralized platform that runs smart contracts,” it just refers to a special type of software program. It may or may not have legal implications and still requires a traditional legal framework around it if it is to be used as part of a legal transaction. Designed from the ground up as a platform for running arbitrary computer programs, Ethereum lent itself naturally to the creation of tokens on top of its platform. Using an Ethereum smart contract, a software developer can (comparatively) easily create a token with any amount of supply, distribution goals, or custom logic. The Ethereum smart contract formed the basis for most of what we call tokens today.

At a very high level, most NFTs are part of the Ethereum blockchain, although other blockchains have implemented their own versions of NFTs. Ethereum is a cryptocurrency, like Bitcoin or Dogecoin, but its blockchain also keeps track of who is holding and trading NFTs. Anything digital could be sold as an NFT

¹ H. Naderi, A. Shojaei, R. Ly, “Autonomous construction safety incentive mechanism using blockchain-enabled tokens and vision-based techniques,” *Automation in Construction* 153, 2023, art. 104959.

² J.D. Pretorius, “Cabinets of curiosities for the postcolony II: Tokens. Collections I–V,” [in:] *Connectivity and Creativity in Times of Conflict*, eds. K. Vaes, J. Verlinden, Antwerp 2023, pp. 245–249, <https://doi.org/10.26530/9789401496476-050>.

³ M. Heckel, F. Waldenberger, *The Future of Financial Systems in the Digital Age Perspectives from Europe and Japan*, Singapore 2022, <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/53375> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

(including articles from Quartz⁴ and *The New York Times*⁵). NFTs became technically possible when the Ethereum blockchain added support for them as part of a new standard.⁶ Of course, one of the first uses was a game called CryptoKitties, that allowed users to trade and sell virtual kittens. There are dozens of NFT marketplaces in existence, many of which have a specific focus or niche.

Most notable and reputable NFT marketplaces

OpenSea, Foundation Marketplace, Axie Infinity, Larva Labs, CryptoPunks, Rarible NFT Marketplace, SuperRare, Nifty Gateway NFT Marketplace, Mintable NFT Marketplace, and Theta Drop, are all places to transact in NFTs.

OpenSea is the leader in NFT sales, offering all sorts of digital assets on its platform. It's free to sign up and browse the extensive offerings. The platform also supports artists and creators and provides an easy-to-use process for creating your own NFT (known as "minting").

Foundation.app was designed as a simple, no-frills way to bid on digital art. Sales are made using Ethereum. Since the marketplace's launch in early 2021, it has sold more than \$100,000,000 worth of NFTs. Artists are invited to the platform by the Foundation community, and buyers simply need a crypto wallet funded with Ethereum to start making purchases. If you're looking for a quick and easy way to start creating your own NFTs, Foundation probably isn't the best place to begin, but the marketplace offers plenty of artwork that can be perused in a simple format.

Axie Marketplace is the online shop for the video game Axie Infinity. Axies are mythical creatures that can be bought, trained, and pitted against other players' Axies to earn rewards. On Axie Marketplace, players can buy new Axies, as well as entire lands and other items, as NFTs for use within the game. Axie Infinity tokens (called Axie Shards) are built on the Ethereum blockchain, allowing them to be bought and sold on various other NFT marketplaces, as well as on some cryptocurrency exchanges,⁷ such as Coinbase Global.

⁴ S. Subramanian, D. Yanofsky, "We sold the first-ever NFT news article for \$1,800," Quartz, March 22, 2021, <https://qz.com/1984094/quartz-is-selling-the-first-ever-nft-news-article> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

⁵ K. Roose, "Buy this column on the blockchain!," *The New York Times*, March 24, 2021, <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/03/24/technology/nft-column-blockchain.html> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

⁶ "ERC-721 non-fungible token standard," Ethereum, November 19, 2023, <https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/standards/tokens/erc-721/> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

⁷ E. Newbery, "Best cryptocurrency exchanges and apps for 2025," Motley Fool Money, January 13, 2025, <https://www.fool.com/the-ascent/cryptocurrency/best-cryptocurrency-apps/?luri=%2Fcryptocurrency%2Fnft-marketplaces%2F&furi=%2Fcryptocurrency%2Fnft-marketplaces%2F<yp=txt> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

Larva Labs is best known for the viral CryptoPunks NFT project. Originally, given away for free in 2017, some CryptoPunks have since sold for millions of dollars. Larva Labs is also involved in other digital art projects, such as *Autoglyphs*, as well as other Ethereum blockchain-based app development projects. Although Larva Labs' CryptoPunks NFTs are sold out, they can be bid on and bought from various third-party marketplaces. Nevertheless, Larva Labs' various projects, including the Meebits, are worth keeping an eye on, as they can be bid on directly from the company's built-in marketplace.

NBA Top Shot is the National Basketball Association and Women's National Basketball Association's foray into the NFT world. On its marketplace, collectible moments (video clips and play highlights) and art can be purchased from the world's premier basketball leagues.

Rarible is another large marketplace for all sorts of NFTs, similar to OpenSea. A wide array of art, videos, collectibles, and music can be bought, sold, or created on the platform. However, unlike OpenSea, you'll need to use the marketplace's own token, Rarible, to buy and sell on the platform. Rarible is built on the Ethereum blockchain (although artwork can also be managed on OpenSea, using Rarible tokens). The company has partnered with notable companies. Yum! Brands' Taco Bell has listed art on Rarible, and cloud software giant Adobe recently partnered with Rarible to help secure NFT artists' and creators' work.

SuperRare is similar to Rarible, also providing a marketplace for digital creators. The site features art, videos, and 3D images, but collectors can purchase artwork using Ethereum. SuperRare recently announced its own token of the same name based on the Ethereum blockchain. The tokens will be used to find and curate new talent for the marketplace. Like Rarible, SuperRare NFTs can also be bought and sold on OpenSea.

Nifty Gateway has facilitated the sale of some of the most popular digital artists, such as Beeple and singer/musician Grimes. It's an art curation platform powered by the crypto exchange Gemini (controlled by the Winklevoss twins). The NFTs, known as Nifties, are built on Ethereum. Besides being a curated platform, Nifty Gateway also hosts any NFTs purchased, meaning the NFTs aren't stored in your own wallet but are kept for you by Nifty Gateway and Gemini. While this may not work for NFT collectors who want more flexibility with their art investments, Nifty purchases and sales also can be made in fiat currency (e.g., US dollars) without needing to make a cryptocurrency purchase first.

Mintable, backed by billionaire Mark Cuban,⁸ aims to be an open marketplace like OpenSea. To participate in buying and selling NFTs on Mintable, you'll need

⁸ E. Newbery, "Mark Cuban is betting big on NFTs. Should you buy them?," Motley Fool Money, May 1, 2021 <https://www.fool.com/the-ascent/buying-stocks/articles/mark-cuban-is-betting-big-on-nfts-should-you-buy-them/?luri=%2Fcurrency%2Fnft-marketplaces%2F&furi=%2Fcurrency%2Fnft-marketplaces%2F<yp=txt> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

Ethereum. The platform also supports the minting of NFTs for creators of all types (from photographers to musicians) who want to sell their work as digital assets.

An aspiring NFT collector or creator will first need to purchase Ethereum from a cryptocurrency exchange before connecting their wallet to Mintable to facilitate bidding and buying on the marketplace.

Theta is a blockchain platform built for the decentralized distribution of video and television on the internet. The NFT marketplace Theta Drop made its debut in 2021 with the World Poker Tour's digital collectibles. The World Poker Tour was an early adopter of ThetaTV and uses the platform to stream content.

Theta utilizes its own blockchain technology. To participate in the Theta Drop NFT marketplace, you'll need to purchase Theta Token.⁹ Various cryptocurrency exchanges, such as Binance, support Theta, and the tokens and NFTs purchased with them can be stored in a crypto wallet, as well as in Theta's own crypto wallet app.

Brief background of the art market in Africa

The African art market has grown significantly, with more regional and international collectors investing in African art. Auctions like the East African Art Auction, International galleries and collectors are increasingly seeking out African artists, which in return helps enhance the visibility of African art and provides a commercial infrastructure that was lacking in the earlier decades.

Kenya, one of the East African countries, has a vibrant art scene which has recently seen growth and recognition, with new and established gallery spaces, artists' collectives, and studios emerging in various urban areas. There has also been an increase in formal art education at the university level (Kenyatta University) and training at the tertiary level (Buruburu Institute of Art), along with the establishment of art programmes and residencies, such as those offered by the GoDown Arts Centre, Kuona Trust, and recently the Nairobi Contemporary Arts Institute. This has led to an increase in formalized training for artists, that was not available before, particularly for the older generation of Kenyan artists who were largely self-taught.

Interestingly, the 1980s laid the foundation for the dynamic contemporary art scene that Kenya enjoys today within the African art market.

Kenya gained its independence in 1963, which brought to challenges and social, political, and cultural changes that created a desire among artists in the 1980s to search for their identity, grappling with themes of independence, decolonization, and neo-colonization. Nairobi, the capital city of Kenya, became the primary centre

⁹ "Theta Token (crypto: Theta)," The Motley Fool, <https://www.fool.com/quote/crypto/theta/> (accessed: 25.09.2024).

for Kenyan art, attracting artists, both local and international, due to its institutions, galleries, and the presence of expatriates who acted as patrons of the art.

The 1980s marked a shift from “naïve” or purely traditional forms of art to more contemporary and experimental art forms. Shine Tani, a painter, sculptor, and the director of Banana Hill Gallery¹⁰ based in Nairobi, is one of the artists who emerged during the 1980s era. In a conversation, Shine recounted his journey as a committed artist since 1987, enduring the good, the bad, and the ugly of being a visual artist for many years. Although galleries existed, Shine did not receive formal education as an artist, as art was not given significant support by the government at the time. He gained fame among fellow local artists whom he later mentored, providing accommodation and studio space at his home.

The economic struggles of the time meant that the local art market was underdeveloped, and artists often relied on expatriates visiting the country and international buyers for patronage. For example, the Banana Hill Art Studio, that was managed by Shine Tani, received support from friends from Philadelphia, Belgium, and even local friends such as Ngugi Wa Thiong’o (a prolific writer in exile at the time in the USA), and could only meet the artists in Uganda, a neighbouring country to Kenya.

The marketing and business model initially operated on a “trust” basis, where artists would bring their artworks to the gallery with the hope of making sales to walk-in customers. This created a large collection of East African art at the Banana Hill Art Studio. In 2010, Shine Tani realized that Africa faced a huge deficit in art marketing and gallery spaces. He sought collaborative ways to work with regional artists from the African diaspora in Ghana, Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Sudan, Cameroon, South Africa, Uganda, and Tanzania, which led to the creation of the Banana Hill Art Gallery.

The concept of collaboration has become the accepted model on the Kenyan art scene, with artist collectives, such as The Nest Collective,¹¹ emerging as platforms where artists, filmmakers, writers, and performers work together. This period has seen increased inter-African collaborations and exchange programmes with other countries on the continent, creating a more interconnected Pan-African art scene.

With urban spaces in Kenya experiencing an upsurge in the building industry, there is a growing demand from art connoisseurs to buy original art made by African artists, now termed as *home-made* art. This has given the Kenyan youth a career path they would not have followed in the past when art was not widely accepted or appreciated.

¹⁰ “Discover contemporary African art,” Banana Hill Art Gallery, <https://www.bananahillgallery.com> (accessed: 24.09.2024).

¹¹ The Nest Collective, <https://www.thisisthenest.com> (accessed: 24.09.2024).

The Kenyan art scene has now joined the ranks of contemporary African art, undergoing a rigorous transformation from the 1990s to the present and becoming a global visual voice. These changes can be attributed to various factors, from the growing presence of Kenyan artists on the international stage to the emergence of new institutions, such as Kuona Trust (founded in 1995), Nairobi National Museum, Circle Art Gallery (founded in 2012), Ramoma Modern Museum, art fairs and biennales.

Smartphones' impact on the art market

iPhone was launched in 2007, and smartphones have been spreading worldwide ever since. According to a survey by the World Bank Development Research Group (2017),¹² among a population of 1.7 billion adults without bank accounts, over 1.1 billion had mobile phones. The popularization of mobile phones and smartphones has drastically promoted financial inclusion worldwide by enabling people to access mobile payment services. Bitcoin, the first cryptocurrency, as well as blockchain and other distributed ledger technologies (DLTs), were introduced in 2009. Although Bitcoin and other first-generation cryptocurrencies have not been used as payment instruments but rather as speculative investment targets, blockchain and other DLTs have become technological platforms for new payment infrastructures such as Libra.

The increase in the use of technology and digital platforms by Kenyan artists has encouraged new ways to connect with audiences globally. The COVID-19 pandemic expanded the reach of Kenyan art through virtual exhibitions and online auctions. These platforms included initiatives such as Artsy, the African Art Galleries Association, OpenSea, and Foundation (NFT platforms). This has led to diversification of artistic practices through experimentation beyond traditional painting and sculpture to video, performance art, installations, photography, and digital media. There has also been a shift in themes and subject matter, from traditional and post-colonial themes to a wider range of issues such as liminality and urbanization, environmentalism, binary opposition of gender identity, and technological advancement.

The development of online communication tools has created new opportunities to provide services and share the results of one's work via the Internet. It is worth noting that even before the COVID-19 pandemic, the issue of artwork valuation was crucial for artists. The NFT became an important way of artwork monetization for them and the new services providers, and more

¹² World Bank Development Research Group, Finance and Private Sector Development Unit, "Global Financial Inclusion (Global Findex) database 2017," The World Bank Microdata Library, <https://doi.org/10.48529/FKZS-AT21>.

frequently one hears about artists converting their artworks (the results of their work) into NFTs.¹³

On February 28, 2012, an 18-year-old high school student wrote, “If Bitcoin is to achieve mainstream success, it cannot stop at the limited crowds of Internet geeks, libertarians, and privacy advocates that it is hitting now, and it must find some way to attract the mainstream public.”¹⁴ Decentralization is a fundamental part of the clever solution that gave us Bitcoin, the first widely successful digital currency. But decentralization is as old as currency itself. Gold was used as a decentralized currency because it too can be used without referring to a central authority. Someone can trade gold for goods and services with both parties recognizing its value. It has utility as a compact and fungible store of that value. Because of the similarity in concept, many describe Bitcoin as “digital gold,” and Satoshi Nakamoto’s famous white paper uses the metaphor of mining, just like gold, to describe the creation of new coins.

Previous virtual realities differ from the metaverse in an important aspect of NFTs. These are digital certificates of ownership that digitally guarantee a sense of unique ownership. The NFTs are considered to be the fourth illusion. They provide the illusion of digital ownership, as they are mined on a blockchain and cannot be replicated. Through the use of NFTs, digital scarcity is created. Scarcity is the foundation of the economy, yet it was not present before the introduction of blockchain technology. The Metaverse, therefore, offers new opportunities to create a virtual economy with virtual pieces of art that sell for high values. The most famous example of this is likely the Bored Ape virtual imagery, which ranges in price from \$63,000 to \$13,000,000.

The concept of value within the functional properties of a currency is that it is fungible. William Stanley Jevons argued in 1875 that fungible currency was economically more beneficial than payment systems based on barter. The concept of fungibility is still considered valid today. If this definition of value is used, NFTs would not be considered a virtual currency. By definition, an NFT cannot be divided, thus it does not classify as currency. It is likely that value should be determined according to the functional definition of money.

The intersection of African art and NFTs has created a transformative moment in the contemporary art world. This emerging space has allowed African artists to bypass traditional gatekeepers, such as galleries and auction houses, and gain direct access to global audiences. The development of African NFT marketplaces is

¹³ K. Marchewka-Bartkowiak, M. Litwiński, K. Nowak, “Individual work pricing by non-fungible personal tokens (‘NFT gig tokens’)—A new opportunity for gig workers,” [in:] *Digital Labour Markets in Central and Eastern European Countries*, eds. B. Woźniak-Jęchorek, K. Marchewka-Bartkowiak, London 2023, pp. 249–268.

¹⁴ V. Buterin, “Bitcoin adoption opportunity: Teenagers,” *Bitcoin Magazine*, February 28, 2012, <https://bitcoinmagazine.com/culture/bitcoin-adoption-opportunity-teenager-1330407280> (accessed: 24.09.2024).

a growing trend. Platforms such as Momint and Binance NFT Marketplace are creating dedicated spaces for African digital art. These platforms cater specifically to African creators, offering lower minting fees and greater accessibility compared to global platforms, thus enabling broader participation in the space.

Conclusion

The potential for NFTs to revolutionize the African art world is very clear. They offer new opportunities for financial empowerment, cultural expression, technological convergence and innovation, as well as global connectivity. African artists are leveraging NFTs to break through barriers, gain international recognition, and redefine what it means to be an African creator in the digital age.

While the NFT space has seen tremendous growth and innovation, there have been instances of fraud and exploitation. Some of the main loopholes or vulnerabilities in NFT marketplaces include plagiarism and copyright infringement, false attribution, front-running, smart contract vulnerabilities, and marketplace fraud. To mitigate these risks, it is important for both creators and buyers to exercise caution and conduct thorough due diligence when participating in the NFT market. This can be achieved by verifying the authenticity of artworks, researching the reputation of NFT platforms and marketplaces, and staying informed about best practices and emerging trends in the space.

The NFT marketplace is constantly evolving, with new platforms emerging over time and potential risks and scams in the NFT space. Artists should stay informed and prioritize platforms with a strong reputation and track record.

NFT platforms should implement measures such as identity verification, content moderation, and security protocols to enhance trust and security within their ecosystems.

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